

DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF A MULTILINGUAL SAFETY SYSTEM FOR VEHICLES ON CONSTRUCTION SITES

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry, crucial for global economic and infrastructure development, is known for its hazardous nature and high accident rates. Despite advancements in safety practices, construction site vehicle collisions remain a significant concern, exacerbated by limitations in current manual control systems which often suffer from human error, poor visibility, and inadequate safety protocols. This study proposes a multilingual voice-based warning system designed to enhance safety by addressing these limitations. By leveraging on the increasing adoption of voice-based technologies and the substantial growth in digital voice assistant use, the system aims to improve situational awareness and responsiveness through voice alerts in multiple languages, including Yoruba. The system integrates ultrasonic sensors for real-time obstacle detection with a voice alert module that provides warnings in different languages. The design also includes automatic vehicle speed reduction and stopping mechanisms based on obstacle proximity. Simulation results show that the sensing duration of the system is directly proportional to the distance of the obstacle. These demonstrate the system's effectiveness in varying distance scenarios, highlighting its potential to significantly reduce construction site accidents. Future work will involve prototype development and further optimization of the vehicle stopping distance. This multilingual voice-based safety solution is anticipated to enhance construction site safety, addressing current system shortcomings and promoting universal comprehension among diverse worker populations.

Keywords: Safety, Voice alert, Multilingual, Construction site, Vehicle collision

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is a vital sector driving economic growth and infrastructure development globally (Anaman *et al.*, 2007) and conversely, its inherent complexity renders it one of the most hazardous industries worldwide (Hossain *et al.*, 2020). Despite advancements and innovations in construction practices, safety remains a paramount concern, with statistics indicating a persistently high rate of accidents and fatalities within the industry (Zhou *et al.*, 2015). Construction site vehicles are essential for transporting materials, equipment, and workers on construction sites (Dubois *et al.*, 2019). According to Jo *et al.* (2019), vehicle collisions remain a significant subset of accidents in construction environments. However, the existing methods of safety around the truck operation are primarily reliant on manual pedal controls, which are characterised by human error, limited visibility, inadequate safety protocols, and delays in responsiveness, and poor coordination (Stanislaw *et al.* 2017).

Repercussions of vehicle collisions on construction sites are profound, causing not only physical injuries leading to disabilities and loss of life (Melenbrink *et al.*, 2020) but costly property damage, project delays, legal liabilities, detrimental effects on stakeholder morale and public perception which impacts productivity and profitability for

construction companies (Cooney 2016). Therefore, an innovative warning system, capable of appreciable improvement over existing visual warning methods for construction vehicles is required for safety on construction sites (Johnson *et al.*, 2017)

According to Feng *et al.* (2018), voice-based technologies could enable construction workers to perform diverse activities on site using a voice command as they offer hands-free and eye-free operations. It is noteworthy that the adoption of voice-based technology is soaring, with about 3.25b digital voice assistants in use in 2019 and a forecast of 8b users by 2023 (Statistica, 2019). Hence the construction industry cannot afford to lag. No doubt the speed, efficiency, and convenience achieved by voice-based technology could enhance warning systems, improve situational awareness, and promote safe driving practices are essential to address this pressing safety concern, as Hirst & Graham (2020) recognized voice alert systems as effective in alerting individuals to potential hazards promptly. Ogundice *et al.* (2018) ranked difficulty in adapting to safety procedures against traditional practices as the number one factor militating against safety on construction sites. Thus, this innovation aims to accommodate the diverse linguistic backgrounds of native construction workers to ensure universal comprehension

and facilitate a prompt response to warnings, thereby reducing accidents on construction sites. This study aims to develop a multilingual voice-based safety solution that prioritizes inclusivity for efficiency in construction sites while addressing the shortcomings of current warning systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Jo *et al.* (2018) addressed the prevalent issue of accidents in the construction industry, particularly collisions involving workers and heavy equipment. Their developed proximity warning system integrates Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology and the Around View Monitor (AVM) to detect hazardous proximity situations in real-time, alerting workers and equipment operators promptly. The system automatically shuts down the excavator upon detecting an approaching worker, effectively preventing accidents. However, the paper exclusively focused on excavator systems, neglecting broader construction vehicle applications. Also, the emphasis on visual alert warnings overlooks the potential benefits of voice alerts. Future research should aim toward comprehensive systems adaptable to various vehicles and consider alternative alert mechanisms that include slowing down before coming to a complete halt for improved safety outcomes. An embedded system for vehicle cabin safety and security was proposed by Ramya *et al.* (2012), aiming to enhance road safety by monitoring toxic gasses and detecting obstacles. The system integrates existing modules to monitor levels of CO, LPG, and alcohol inside the vehicle, providing alerts via an alarm and SMS through GSM during critical situations. An infrared sensor (IR) detects static obstacles in front of the vehicle, signaling the microcontroller to stop the vehicle to prevent collisions. The hardware used included an Atmel AT89S52 microcontroller interfaced with gas sensing, obstacle detection modules, and analog-to-digital conversion for data processing. The system aims to protect passengers inside the vehicle and pedestrians, contributing to night time safety by avoiding accidents with static obstacles. However, the distance between the vehicle and the static obstacle supported by the IR sensor is three feet, and in future the distance could be increased by replacing the IR sensor with the ultrasonic sensor which can measure up to 6m. Furthermore, the system solely relies on detecting static obstacles using an IR sensor, potentially limiting its effectiveness in dynamic environments where obstacles may change rapidly.

Essien & Chimezie (2023) presented an ultrasonic sensor-based embedded system for vehicular collision detection and alert. Their objective is to enhance road safety by developing an automated anti-collision system that utilizes ultrasonic sensors to detect obstacles and activate an alert mechanism to prevent potential accidents. Integrating an ultrasonic sensor, microcontroller, and alarm system, the method detects objects in real-time and alerts drivers, displaying distance information on an LCD screen. While the system demonstrates efficiency in mitigating collision-related concerns, limitations include factors like sensor

accuracy and environmental conditions. However, a major drawback is that the system just detects objects and sends warnings. Adding automatic braking could help increase safety, especially in cases where the driver does not respond to the warning alerts.

In Vehicles Auto Collision Detection and Avoidance Protocol by Almutairi *et al.* (2022), an artificial intelligence (AI) - based system was used to prevent road accidents through the integration of AI and global positioning system technologies. The work introduced a two-layered approach for vehicle/obstacle detection with auto warning mechanisms for collision detection and avoidance, along with GPS and video camera-based alert systems for timely driver rescue in accidents. Using image processing, radar systems, and live video cameras, the system detects obstacles, computes distances, and identifies potential collisions, triggering alerts and necessary actions such as auto brakes and warning alarms. However, the system may not work well in areas with irregular internet connectivity.

Real-time Vision-Based Collision Warning System for Heavy Equipment in Construction Sites by Son *et al.* (2019) used a real-time vision-based collision warning system designed to enhance safety in construction sites by detecting and monitoring potential collisions between heavy equipment and workers using visual data from cameras installed on the equipment. Employing a privacy-by-design approach, the system estimates workers' positions in three dimensions (3D) and utilizes a distance-based warning system with varying zones to alert operators of potential collision risks. The system primarily focuses on collision avoidance with workers and lacks exploration into preventing collisions with other equipment or static obstacles. The presence of other equipment and obstacles should be considered for safety enhancement.

Narayanan *et al.* (2024) developed an Automatic Microcontroller-Based Crash Avoidance System. The work makes use of ultrasonic sensors integrated with an Arduino Uno microcontroller to gauge distances between the vehicle and potential obstacles, triggering automatic braking when necessary to mitigate collision risks. Despite its effectiveness in reducing the likelihood of accidents, a notable limitation of the system lies in its automatic brake application without prior warning. To address this concern, the authors suggest incorporating a warning signal that is culturally inclusive to enhance driver awareness and overall system effectiveness, thereby mitigating potential discomfort associated with abrupt braking maneuvers.

SYSTEM DESIGN

The safety system for vehicles on construction sites is designed to enhance the safety of workers and reduce vehicle collisions. A conceptual diagram presented in Figure 1 shows a typical construction site where vehicles convey materials in and out of the site. An embedded (safety) system is attached in front of each vehicle to monitor their proximity to obstacles. The system architecture comprises hardware and software components working together to

achieve real-time monitoring and response. The system integrates sensing, voice alerts, and automatic actions to improve situational awareness and prevent accidents.

A theoretical model of the safety system was developed and tested in Proteus. This simulation approach allowed for refining the design and verifying its performance before physical prototyping. A flowchart outlined the control logic for obstacle detection and response. The algorithm was tested in various scenarios to ensure it effectively managed responses to different obstacle distances. Simulation results were reviewed to assess system performance and make adjustments. This iterative process refined the design based

on performance metrics, enhancing reliability before physical implementation.

System Architecture

This section describes the circuit diagram, control algorithm, and working principles. Figure 2 depicts the circuit connections. The Trigger and Echo pins of the ultrasonic sensor are connected to pin D10 and pin D11 of the Arduino board respectively. The VCC and the GND pins of the sensor and that of the mp3 player (DFPlayer Mini) are connected to the power supply unit's 5V positive and negative rails. Pin D3 (Rx) and pin D4 (Tx) of the

Figure 1: Conceptual Diagram of the Multilingual Safety System

Figure 2: Circuit Diagram of the Multilingual Safety System

Arduino board are configured as a serial port using a software Serial library. These pins are then connected to the Tx and Rx pins of the DFP layer Mini module respectively. However, a 1kΩ resistor is connected between pin D4 of the Arduino board and the Rx pin of the DFP layer Mini module.

The Base pin of a power Darlington transistor (TIP142) is connected through a 10 kΩ resistor to pin D9 of the Arduino pin. While the Emitter pin of this transistor is connected to the common ground of the circuit, the Collector is connected to one terminal of the relay's coil. The other terminal of the coil is connected to a 12V positive rail. This makes the relay to be in a series connection with the transistor. A flywheel diode is connected in reverse bias parallel to the relay's coil to oppose the feedback current generated from the coil. The common pin of the relay is connected to the 12V positive rail while the normally open (NO) of the relay is connected to a terminal of the servo motor. The other terminal of the motor is connected to the circuit's common ground while the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) pin of the motor is connected to pin D5 of the Arduino board. A 4Ω 3W speaker is connected to SPK+ and SPK- of the mp3 module.

The pseudocode for the control software is shown in Figure 3. The ultrasonic sensor, in this circuit, continuously measures the distance between itself and the obstacle. When the distance is greater than or equal to 6 meters, the vehicle maintains its current speed. However, when the distance is less than 6 meters but greater than 3 meters, a voice, (“Speed reduction activated!”/”*Ìdírwo’ wà lònà, òkò dínwò eré*”), designated as the first alert is activated and the speed of the vehicle is reduced. Then the system returns to check for obstacles and their proximity. If an obstacle is still detected and its distance is less than 3 meters, a voice, (“Vehicle stopping activated!”/”*Ìdírwo’ sí wà lònà, òkò dúró*”), designated as a second alert is activated and the vehicle is put to a stop.

Justification of choice of components

Arduino Uno: The Arduino Uno microcontroller board was chosen for its versatility, ease of use, and wide availability of libraries that support the integration of sensors, actuators, and communication modules (Langis, 2015). Its digital and analog I/O pins make it suitable for handling multiple inputs and outputs, essential for this project (ARDUINO, 2021).

Ultrasonic Sensor (HC-SR04): This sensor was selected for its reliability in measuring distances using sound waves. It can detect obstacles up to 6 meters away with reasonable accuracy, making it ideal for proximity sensing in dynamic environments like construction sites (Ercan & Mohammed,2020 ; Obuhuma *et al.*,2019 ; Singh *et al.*, 2021).

DFPlayer Mini Module: This module was chosen for its ability to play audio files directly from an SD card, supporting the project's goal of providing audible voice

alerts (AGIN *et al* 2019). Its compact size and simple interface with Arduino make it a practical choice for embedded applications (Sakthivel *et al.*,2024).

Power Darlington Transistor (TIP142): The TIP142 was selected due to its high current gain and ability to drive larger loads, such as a relay with minimal control current. This is crucial for ensuring reliable switching of the relay in response to control signals from the Arduino (Khan *et al.*, 2014).

Relay Module: The relay is used to control the power supply to the servo motor based on signals from the Arduino. It was selected for its ability to handle higher currents and voltages than what the Arduino can directly manage, ensuring safe and efficient operation of the motor (Paul *et al.*, 2019).

Servo Motor: The servo motor was chosen for its precision in control and ease of interfacing with the Arduino. It provides the mechanical actuation required to adjust the vehicle's speed or bring it to a stop, based on obstacle detection (GeeksforGeeks, 2024).

Flywheel Diode: The flywheel diode was selected to protect the circuit from voltage spikes generated by the relay's coil when it is de-energized. This helps to prevent damage to other components in the circuit (Mosaad *et al.*,2021).

Speaker: A 4Ω 3W speaker was selected to produce clear and audible voice alerts in both English and Yoruba. The choice ensures that alerts can be heard clearly in the noisy environment of a construction site (Joshi *et al.*,2024).

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Start
Select preferred language (English or Yoruba)
Check for Obstacle:
  If an obstacle is detected:
    Measure the distance to the obstacle
    If 6m < distance < 3m:
      Activate 1st Voice Alert (obstacle detected)
      Vehicle speed automatically reduces
    Else if distance < 3m:
      Activate 2nd Voice Alert (object still detected)
      Vehicle automatically stops
  else:
    Maintain current vehicle speed
End
    
```

Figure 3: Pseudocode for the Multilingual Safety System

Communication Architecture within the Circuit Diagram

The Arduino Uno serves as the brain of the system, coordinating data flow and control signals between various components. It processes input data from the ultrasonic sensor and sends commands to the DFPlayer Mini and the servo motor.

The Trigger and Echo pins of the HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor are connected to pins D10 and D11 of the Arduino.

The Arduino sends a trigger pulse to the ultrasonic sensor, which then sends back an echo signal based on the time it takes for the pulse to bounce off an obstacle. The time interval is processed by the Arduino to calculate the distance to the obstacle.

The DFPlayer Mini is connected to the Arduino via software Serial on pins D3 (Rx) and D4 (Tx). Serial communication is used to send commands from the Arduino to the DFPlayer Mini. This allows the Arduino to instruct the DFPlayer Mini to play specific audio files (voice alerts) based on obstacle proximity. A $1k\Omega$ resistor is placed between the Arduino's Tx pin and the DFPlayer's Rx pin to prevent damage to the module due to voltage differences.

The Arduino controls the base of the TIP142 Darlington transistor via pin D9. A digital signal from the Arduino switches the transistor on or off, which in turn controls the relay. The relay then manages the power supply to the servo motor, enabling or disabling its operation. The Arduino uses Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) on pin D5 to control the motor's speed.

The servo motor receives its control signal from pin D5 of the Arduino. The Arduino uses PWM signals to adjust the servo motor's position, controlling the vehicle's speed or stopping it based on the distance data from the ultrasonic sensor.

The circuit is powered by two voltage rails, 5V from the Arduino for the sensor and DFPlayer Mini, and 12V for the relay and servo motor. The Arduino manages power distribution, ensuring each component receives the necessary voltage for operation.

Theoretical Foundation for the Circuit Design

Ohm's Law and Voltage Dividers

Ohm's Law: The relationship between voltage (V), current (I), and resistance (R) is foundational to the circuit design. Ohm's Law ($V = IR$) is applied across various components to ensure that the correct voltage levels are maintained for reliable operation, particularly in the communication between the Arduino and the DFPlayer Mini module.

Voltage Dividers: The use of a $1k\Omega$ resistor between the Arduino's Tx pin and the DFPlayer's Rx pin functions as part of a voltage divider. This helps reduce the 5V logic level from the Arduino to a safe level for the DFPlayer Mini, which operates at 3.3V, thereby protecting the module from potential damage.

Kirchhoff's Laws:

Kirchhoff's Current Law (KCL): This law states that the sum of currents entering a junction must equal the sum of currents leaving the junction. This principle is applied in the power distribution across the circuit, ensuring that the current supplied by the power rails is appropriately divided among components like the ultrasonic sensor, DFPlayer Mini, and the relay.

Transistor Switching and Amplification:

Darlington Transistor (TIP142): The use of a Darlington transistor leverages its high current gain, allowing a small current from the Arduino to control a larger current through the relay coil. This principle of current amplification is critical in controlling high-power components with low-power signals from the microcontroller.

Switching: The transistor operates as a switch in this circuit, controlled by the Arduino's digital output. When the base of the transistor is driven high, it allows current to flow from the collector to the emitter, thus energizing the relay coil.

Electromagnetic Induction:

Electromagnetic Induction: This is the underlying principle of relay operation, where an electric current generates a magnetic field, enabling the mechanical movement required to switch the motor circuit on or off.

Pulse Width Modulation (PWM):

Motor Speed Control: The servo motor's speed and position are controlled using PWM signals from the Arduino. PWM is a technique where the amount of power delivered to the motor is controlled by varying the duty cycle of the digital signal. This allows the motor to operate at different speeds, facilitating smooth acceleration, deceleration, or stopping of the vehicle based on the proximity of obstacles.

Design considerations

In designing the vehicle safety system circuit, several key considerations were taken into account to ensure functionality and reliability. Compatibility was crucial; for example, the Arduino operates at 5V, while the DFPlayer Mini operates at 3.3V, requiring a resistor to protect the DFPlayer from potential damage. The power supply unit was chosen to reliably provide 5V and 12V outputs to power all components without causing voltage drops or overheating.

The ultrasonic sensor's accuracy and response time were central to the design. The system assumes the sensor will provide reliable distance measurements within the 4-meter range, with thresholds set at 3 meters and 6 meters to ensure timely vehicle response. The control logic was kept simple to enhance reliability, with straightforward thresholds for activating alerts to minimize errors and simplify debugging.

Safety was a priority, so a flywheel diode was included to protect the transistor from damage caused by back EMF from the relay coil. The design also assumes minimal electrical noise and incorporates basic measures to handle any potential noise issues. The physical layout was designed to be compact, considering space constraints and thermal management. The design presumes that the components will not overheat under normal conditions, though additional cooling may be added if needed. Lastly, the design was made modular to allow for future expansions or

upgrades, ensuring that individual components can be tested or replaced independently. This approach supports long-term adaptability and ease of maintenance.

SYSTEM OPERATIONS

This section discusses the functioning of the system during its execution. It involves the processes, activities, and interactions that occur within the voice alert safety system for optimal functionality.

Detection Phase: The ultrasonic sensors continuously scan the surroundings of the vehicle, emitting ultrasonic waves and measuring the time taken for the waves to bounce back. These measurements determine the distances to nearby objects, ensuring that any potential obstacles are detected in real-time.

Table 1: Simulation Results

Voltage (V)	Distance (m)	Sensing Duration (ms)
0	0	0.23
0.5	1	6.49
1	2	13.04
1.5	3	19.53
2	4	26.02
2.5	5	32.51
3	6	39.06
3.5	7	45.80
4	8	52.04
4.5	10	58.59
5	11	65.08

Data Processing: The Microcontroller Unit (Arduino) receives distance measurements from the sensors and processes them to assess the presence and proximity of obstacles. This analysis forms the basis for subsequent actions within the system, determining the necessary responses based on the detected distances.

Alert Generation and Response Implementation: When obstacles are detected within a specified distance, the voice alert module generates a voice alert in the selected language (Yoruba or English). Simultaneously, the system triggers alert to capture the driver's attention and sends commands to the vehicle's control interface. Depending on the proximity of the obstacle, the vehicle's speed is either reduced or the vehicle is brought to a complete stop, ensuring automatic response to potential hazards.

SIMULATION AND DISCUSSION OF THE MULTILINGUAL SAFETY SYSTEM

The simulation on Proteus provides a virtual environment to test the functionality of the safety system in a controlled setting. By integrating this simulation into the system design documentation, engineers can gain insights into how the system behaves under different scenarios before prototypes are constructed. Proteus was used to model and test the circuit design virtually. This software allowed for the analysis of circuit behaviour without physical

construction which enables early identification of potential issues and verification of the design's functionality.

Component Configuration

For simulation purposes, a 1kΩ variable resistor is connected at the test pin of the ultrasonic sensor. Variations in the resistances account for the obstacle's proximity distance computation. The ultrasonic sensor was connected to the Arduino board for distance measurement, while the DFPlayer Mini provided voice alerts through serial communication. A relay and transistor controlled the servo motor, ensuring coordinated responses based on sensor input.

Test Setup

A variable resistor simulated different obstacle distances, and data on voltage, distance, and sensing duration were recorded. This setup helped evaluate how the system responded to varying distances and obstacle proximities. The resistance is varied and the corresponding voltage, distance, and sensing duration were recorded as shown in Table 1.

Analysis

Data were analysed by plotting sensing duration versus distance, revealing the relationship between obstacle distance and system response. This analysis identified optimal settings for the system's alert triggers. The relationship between the sensing duration and the obstacle's proximity is charted as shown in Figure 4.

From Figure 4, it shows that the sensing duration of the system is directly proportional to the distance of the obstacle. As the distance increases, the sensing duration also increases. Therefore, an optimum distance should be sought. It is after this period that the vehicle's speed is automatically reduced or stopped.

The ultrasonic sensor continuously measures the distance between the vehicle and obstacles, allowing the system to detect potential hazards early.

Figure 4: Sensing Duration against Obstacle’s Distance

The system provides voice notifications in English and Yoruba to ensure that construction vehicle drivers who are usually natives, in this case Yorubas are able to understand and benefit from advancement in technology regardless of their linguistic background. This inclusivity helps in reducing the likelihood of miscommunication and enhances safety for a diverse workforce. Based on distance measurements, the system automatically triggers actions such as speed reduction or stopping the vehicle therefore minimizing the chance of human error and ensuring prompt reactions to potential collisions.

Unlike traditional safety systems that may rely solely on visual or single-language audio alerts, this system incorporates multilingual voice alerts. This feature addresses the diverse linguistic needs of construction workers, improving comprehension and response times across a varied workforce. Also, while many current systems focus either on visual alerts or automated controls, this system integrates both. It not only provides immediate voice warnings but also automates vehicle responses (e.g., speed reduction or stopping) based on sensor data, combining proactive and reactive safety measures.

The design is straightforward, making it easy to implement and maintain. It also allows for future expansion, such as adding more sensors or features, without requiring a complete redesign. This scalability is a key advantage over more complex or rigid systems.

Generation of tuning parameters to also serve as limitations of the Circuit diagram

Tuning Parameters:

Distance Thresholds: The ultrasonic sensor triggers the first alert when the obstacle is between 3 and 6 meters away and the second alert when the obstacle is 3 meters or closer. These thresholds can be adjusted based on specific safety requirements and testing outcomes.

Speed Reduction Values: The system reduces vehicle speed by a predefined amount when the first alert is activated. This value should be optimized based on vehicle performance and safety standards.

Response Time: The time delay between detecting an obstacle and activating the alerts can be tuned to balance responsiveness and avoid false alarms.

Limitations

The ultrasonic sensor’s accuracy can be affected by environmental factors such as dust, rain, or temperature, which may impact the reliability of distance measurements. Though the alert is inside the vehicle in extremely noisy construction environments, voice alerts may be less effective if they are not loud enough or if there is too much background noise. This could impact the system’s ability to effectively communicate warnings. There may be a delay between obstacle detection and the system’s response (speed reduction or stopping), which could potentially affect safety if not properly tuned.

CONCLUSION

The study presented the design of a multilingual voice alert safety system for construction workers comprising the architecture, system operation, and the simulation. The system incorporates the traditional culture of the construction workers, and the use case here is Yoruba language to improve the usability of the system. The future works will focus on prototyping and the computation of the stopping distance of the vehicle.

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